

Promoting Standardised and FAIR Data Sharing

In Haemoglobinopathies Research

Report

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Abbreviations

ARISE	African Research and Innovative Initiative for Sickle Cell Education
COST	European Cooperation in Science and Technology
eCRF	Electronic Case Report Form
ENROL	European Rare Blood Disorders Platform
ERN	European Reference Network
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
FHIR	Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resource
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GenoMed4AI	Genomics and Personalized Medicine for All through Artificial Intelligence in Haematological Diseases
INHERENT	International Hemoglobinopathy Research Network
HELIOS	Haemoglobinopathies in European Liaison of Medicine and Science
HemaFAIR	Fostering F.A.I.R. Data and Standards in Rare Haematological Diseases
HPO	Human Phenotype Ontology
ITC	Inclusiveness Target Countries
ITHANET	Information and database community portal for haemoglobinopathies
KF	Key Findings
NGS	Next Generation Sequencing
OMOP	Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership
ORDO	Orphanet Rare Disease Ontology
RAD	Rare Anaemia Disorder
RADeep	Rare Anaemias Disorders European Epidemiological Platform
REDCap	Research Electronic Data Capture Platform
RHD	Rare Haematological Disorders
SCD	Sickle Cell Disorders
SCDO	Sickle Cell Disease Ontology
THALAMOSS	THALassaemia MOdular Stratification System for personalised therapy of beta-thalassaemia.
VCF	Variant Call Format
WES	Whole Exome Sequencing
WG	Working Group
WGS	Whole Genome Sequencing

1. Executive Summary

The **HELIOS COST Action (CA22119)** aims to create a pan-European network addressing the challenges of haemoglobinopathies, leveraging multidisciplinary expertise to improve diagnosis, care, and research. Working Group 3 (WG3) focuses on data management, sharing, and analysis to promote adopting standardised and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles in haemoglobinopathy-related research.

Deliverable D3.1, titled *Report on Existing Data (Initial Release)*, provides an overview of the state of haemoglobinopathy datasets across HELIOS participating centres from Europe and beyond. It highlights efforts to map available data, identifies gaps in accessibility and standardisation, and aims to propose actionable guidelines to harmonise data sharing.

Key Findings

- **Geographic Data Gaps:** Haemoglobinopathy data are stored mainly locally, limiting cross-border research.
- **Limited Availability of Advanced Data Types:** Few datasets contain next-generation sequencing (NGS), metabolomics, or advanced disease-specific methodologies.
- **Lack of Standardisation:** Data is often stored in non-standard formats, making integration difficult.
- **Technological Heterogeneity:** Institutions use different data storage and processing tools, reducing interoperability.
- **Limited Data Accessibility:** Most datasets are siloed and not readily available for collaborative research.
- **Willingness to Collaborate:** Despite barriers, stakeholders show strong interest in federated data-sharing approaches.

In response, WG3 has set a goal of developing guidelines for data interoperability and FAIR compliance. These will include recommendations for harmonised data collection protocols, a framework for anonymised case sharing, and preliminary steps towards building a FAIR web-based database to centralise unpublished diagnostic data.

This deliverable establishes the groundwork for addressing the challenges of data standardisation and accessibility, enabling robust multi-centre research and fostering international collaboration. The next phase will focus on implementing these guidelines, testing the database, and refining tools for

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genotype-phenotype analysis, ensuring alignment with FAIR principles and the overarching goals of the HELIOS Action.

2. Introduction

Haemoglobinopathies, such as Sickle Cell Disease (SCD) and Thalassaemia syndromes, are the most common monogenic diseases globally, with significant public health and research implications (Modell and Darlison 2008). These disorders are highly prevalent in regions including the Mediterranean, Sub-Saharan Africa, and Southeast Asia. Still, global migration trends have led to their widespread presence across Europe and other parts of the world (Piel et al. 2014; Canatan et al. 2021; Aguiar et al. 2016; Angastiniotis et al. 2021). Despite their growing prevalence, the research community faces challenges due to fragmented data availability, inconsistent standardisation, and limited adherence to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles (Canatan et al. 2021; Russo et al. 2019; Wilkinson et al. 2016).

HELIOS COST Action CA22119 (<https://heliosaction.eu/>) addresses these challenges by fostering a pan-European network that advances knowledge, enhances patient outcomes, and builds collaborations across clinical, molecular, and computational domains. Working Group 3 (WG3) objectives are to improve data management, sharing, and analysis within HELIOS. Recognising the centrality of high-quality data, WG3 is committed to enabling robust multi-centre studies and facilitating compliance with FAIR principles.

D3.1 The Deliverable of the Report on Existing Data (Initial Release) is a critical first step in mapping the haemoglobinopathy data landscape. The report focuses on:

1. Mapping existing haemoglobinopathy-related datasets, including public repositories and unpublished data.
2. Assessing current levels of data standardisation and adherence to FAIR principles.
3. Proposing actionable recommendations to improve data interoperability and sharing across stakeholders.

WG3 addresses these areas to provide the foundation for large-scale studies and enhance stakeholder collaboration.

This work aligns with previous efforts in the field, such as the Rare Anaemias Disorders European

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Epidemiological (RADeep) platform, Thalassemia Modular Stratification System for Personalized Therapy of Beta-Thalassemia (THALAMOSS), ITHANET, GenoMed4ALL, and HemaFAIR initiatives (Table S1). The findings and recommendations presented here will support the development of harmonised tools and frameworks to drive future discoveries and improve patient care.

3. Brief Overview of Working Group (WG3) Composition and Activities

WG3 comprises 101 participants, including 61 women and 40 men, representing 21 countries. The group includes members from two Near Neighbour Countries and one International Partner Country. Of these participants, 68 are from Inclusiveness Target Countries, and 57 are Young Researchers and Innovators. The composition of WG3 showcases a well-balanced representation of experts and early-career professionals, an inclusive gender ratio, and diverse geographical participation. Furthermore, the group brings together specialists from various disciplines, including bioinformaticians, data experts, physicists, biochemists, researchers, and ethics experts. This diversity underscores a strong commitment to the COST Association's excellence and inclusiveness policy.

Dr. Francesco Cremonesi leads WG3 and is a distinguished researcher at the INRIA Institute. He specialises in federated learning and machine learning and their applications in healthcare and clinical domains. His work focuses on innovative data management, sharing, and analysis approaches, aligning with WG3's mission to enhance FAIR data practices and promote effective collaboration across diverse research disciplines. Dr. Cremonesi's expertise drives the development of cutting-edge solutions that balance privacy, interoperability, and data-driven insights in healthcare.

During the first two years of the HELIOS COST Action, WG3 has conducted monthly meetings, providing a platform for discussing progress, addressing challenges, and planning activities. A distinctive aspect of these meetings is encouraging WG3 members to share their work through brief, informal presentations. This approach promotes the identification of collaborative research opportunities and facilitates knowledge exchange within the group.

In addition to its regular meetings, WG3 has emphasised building knowledge capacity within the group. It has organised online webinars to train members, the broader network, and the public on the FAIR principles, enhancing understanding of data management and shareability. Lastly, the group developed a data mapping

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and availability survey to assess the network's data landscape, providing valuable insights into existing resources and gaps. This initiative supports WG3's overarching goal of fostering collaboration and improving data management practices across the network. The survey outcomes will be explored in more detail in the following sections.

4. Data Mapping and Availability Survey

A web-based survey was conducted to establish a comprehensive landscape of available data, enabling researchers to identify compatible datasets and foster new collaborations. The survey was administered via the Research Electronic Data Capture (REDCap) platform, a secure and user-friendly application for building and managing surveys and databases. Designed to collect high-level information on haemoglobinopathy data availability, formats, and FAIRness, the survey included targeted questions about dataset availability for haemoglobinopathy research.

Participants included healthcare professionals, data analysts, and researchers who had previously responded to the HELIOS Personal Data Declaration and Consent survey. This approach ensured ethical compliance and provided valuable insights into data management practices across participating centres. A comprehensive questionnaire was developed to collect detailed information about haemoglobinopathy data, focusing on its availability, formats, and adherence to FAIR principles. The complete survey instrument is included in Appendix A. In summary, the survey aimed to assess:

- **Dataset availability** (e.g., laboratory tests, imaging, omics data).
- **Data storage and standardisation** (e.g., adherence to FAIR principles).
- **Collaboration and data-sharing preferences** (e.g., centralised vs. federated approaches).
- **Open-ended feedback** on barriers to **data integration, governance, and research collaborations.**

4.1 Survey Respondents & Data Collection

Key Finding 1 (KF1): Geographical Coverage and Data Availability

The survey collected 48 responses from 23 countries, including 15 from European Union (EU) member states and 8 from non-EU countries. Participants represented a broad range of professional backgrounds, emphasising the interdisciplinary nature of haemoglobinopathy research (**Table 1**). These included healthcare professionals, bioinformaticians, ethics and legal experts, data scientists, and clinical researchers, each contributing to various aspects of data management, analysis, and application in haemoglobinopathy studies.

Table 1: Professional background of survey respondents. This table presents the distribution of survey respondents based on their professional background, highlighting the multidisciplinary expertise contributing to haemoglobinopathy research. Some responses declared more than one professional background.

Profession	Number of participants (N)
Diagnosis	23
Molecular research	23
Clinical research or patient management	27
Patients or patient advocates	8
Data management and analysis	12
Other health professional (nurse, psychologist, genetic counselling)	5
Policymaker	4
Not currently involved in haemoglobinopathies	2

As shown in **Figure 1**, respondents reported diverse roles within the field. The most common areas of involvement were molecular research, clinical project management, and diagnostics. Additional roles included patient advocacy, policymaking, and data management. A few participants were not currently engaged in haemoglobinopathy-related work, while others represented the private sector or entrepreneurial

initiatives. This diversity highlights the inclusive and collaborative nature of the HELIOS network and underscores the importance of broad engagement in standardised data-sharing strategies.

Figure 1: Current professional involvement of survey respondents in haemoglobinopathies research. Bar chart depicting the roles and areas of participation of respondents. Most are active in molecular research, clinical project management, or diagnostics. Other roles included data management, patient advocacy, and policymaking. A minority of respondents do not work in haemoglobinopathy-related fields, indicating a diverse professional reach.

Regarding the specific diseases being studied, the most common focus was Sickle Cell Disease (SCD; [ORPHA: 275752](#)), followed by Beta-thalassaemia ([ORPHA: 848](#)) and Alpha-thalassaemia ([ORPHA: 846](#)). Approximately 35.4% of participants reported working on all three conditions, while around 17% indicated they were not currently involved in haemoglobinopathy-related research (**Figure 2**). These findings underscore the diversity of research priorities within the HELIOS network and point to key areas where harmonisation of data collection efforts could be incredibly impactful.

Figure 2: Distribution of survey respondents by disease focus. Bar chart showing the number of respondents working on specific haemoglobinopathy-related conditions. SCD was the most frequently studied, followed by Beta-thalassaemia and Alpha-thalassaemia. Fewer respondents reported studying other haemoglobinopathies or not currently working in the field.

Figure 3 presents a Venn diagram of respondents working on Alpha-thalassaemia, Beta-thalassaemia, and SCD to further illustrate the overlap in disease focus. The substantial intersection indicates that over one-third of participants study all three conditions, demonstrating HELIOS's integrated and multidisciplinary research landscape. This overlap also highlights the potential for unified data harmonisation strategies across these closely related conditions.

Figure 3: Overlap in disease focus among survey respondents. Venn diagram illustrating the proportion of respondents working on Alpha-thalassaemia, Beta-thalassaemia, and Sickle Cell Disease. Approximately 35.4% of participants are involved in research on all three conditions, reflecting the integrated and multidisciplinary research landscape across the HELIOS network.

4.2 Participation in International Projects

Key Finding 2 (KF2): International Collaboration in Haemoglobinopathy Research

Nearly half of the respondents were actively engaged in international projects related to haemoglobinopathies. Respondents' participation in these projects highlights the breadth of global collaborations aimed at enhancing research, diagnosis, and treatment for conditions such as sickle cell disease and thalassemia (Table S1). Table S1 overviews key projects that advance research, data integration, and patient care in haemoglobinopathies. These initiatives focus on enhancing research capacity, promoting standardised data-sharing frameworks, and fostering global collaboration. The projects span across Africa, Europe, and worldwide, addressing challenges related to data interoperability, FAIR principles, artificial intelligence, and disease registries to support improved diagnosis, treatment, and research innovation.

Respondents' participation in other international projects for haemoglobinopathies

Figure 4: Respondents' participation in other

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international projects related to haemoglobinopathies. Bar chart showing the number of survey respondents involved in international initiatives. INHERENT had the highest level of participation, followed by ERN-EuroBloodNet and ARISE. Fewer respondents indicated involvement in other or regional initiatives such as Sickle in Africa. These findings highlight the existing engagement of HELIOS participants in complementary collaborative networks.

As illustrated in **Figure 4**, INHERENT recorded the highest level of participation among survey respondents, reflecting its central role in standardising and integrating SCD patient data across institutions. ERN-EuroBloodNet and ARISE also showed strong involvement, underlining the importance of European-wide initiatives in addressing rare haematological disorders. A smaller but relevant proportion of respondents participated in regional efforts like “Sickle In Africa”, while the “Other” category indicates additional international initiatives not explicitly listed in the survey.

This collective engagement demonstrates the increasing emphasis on standardisation, data interoperability, and FAIR principles in haemoglobinopathy research, which are critical for advancing worldwide diagnosis, treatment, and patient care.

4.3 Data availability and Geographical distribution

Key Finding 3 (KF3): Variability in Data Availability Across Regions

The survey results reveal significant disparities in the availability of haemoglobinopathy-related datasets across different regions. The geographical distribution of respondents included countries across Europe, the Mediterranean, Sub-Saharan Africa, and Southeast Asia, as shown in **Figure 5**.

Figure 5: Geographic distribution of survey respondents. Map illustrating the locations of the 45 respondents who participated in the HELIOS haemoglobinopathy data mapping survey. The responses span 21 countries, including the European Union and non-EU regions, covering Inclusiveness Target Countries (ITCs) and non-ITCs. This geographic diversity highlights the broad scope of international collaboration while underscoring regional disparities in data availability.

While core clinical datasets—such as laboratory tests, patient demographics, and genotype data—are widely accessible, more specialised datasets, including imaging, coded diagnosis, and omics-related data, are far less available. After filtering out respondents who reported having no data, the most commonly collected data types were those typically generated through routine clinical care. As shown in **Figure 6**, 34 out of 37 respondents confirmed the availability of laboratory test data, followed by 32 for patient demographics and 30 for genotype data. In contrast, clinical notes (21), imaging (19), procedures and treatments (17), and coded diagnosis (16) were moderately available. At the lower end, metabolomics (3), WGS (2), transcriptomics (2), and proteomics (1) were the least reported data types.

Regarding data collection frequency, nearly all respondents who reported having imaging data indicated only a single time point of collection. This limitation, along with the small sample sizes typical of rare diseases, further restricts the usability of the data. For example, only two respondents reported having more than 1,000 samples for laboratory tests, while sample sizes were consistently below 100 for the least-available data types.

To help interpret dataset accessibility, responses were grouped into three categories:

- **Widely Available Data:** Laboratory tests, patient demographics, and genotype data, with 28–32 respondents confirming availability.
- **Moderately Available Data:** Clinical notes, imaging, coded treatments, and coded diagnoses, with 16–21 respondents indicating access.
- **Limited Availability Data:** Omics-related data (WES, WGS, transcriptomics, proteomics), fibroscan results, claims data, and service usage records, with only 1–10 respondents reporting availability.

This tiered view highlights the urgent need for improved data infrastructures, standardised models, and increased capacity for collecting longitudinal and high-dimensional data across sites (**Figure 6**).

A regional comparison between Inclusiveness Target Countries (ITCs) and non-ITC countries further underscores disparities in data accessibility. As shown in **Table 2**, both groups reported universal access to at least one core clinical data type. However, non-ITC countries consistently reported a greater availability of additional data types.

Figure 6: Availability of different data types reported by survey respondents. Stacked bar chart showing the availability of various data types in haemoglobinopathy research. Data is categorised as unavailable (red), available cross-sectionally (dark green), available longitudinally (light green), or unknown (yellow). While laboratory tests, demographic data, and genotype data were most frequently available, omics datasets, such as transcriptomics, proteomics, and whole-genome sequencing (WGS), were reported by only a few respondents.

Table 2: Regional differences in data availability between ITC and non-ITC countries. CD: Core Data (Laboratory tests, Demographics, Genotype); ODT: Other Data Type.

Geographic group	At least 1 CD	At least 1 ODT	At least 3 ODTs	At least 5 ODTs
ITC country	100%	73%	47%	22%
non-ITC country	100%	100%	78%	44%

These findings suggest that although access to core clinical datasets is comparable across regions, non-ITC countries report greater availability of diverse and advanced data types, including imaging, coded diagnosis, and treatment records.

Harmonised data collection practices, improved data-sharing infrastructures, and increased investment in standardised data systems are needed to address these disparities. Strengthening international collaboration and aligning data management approaches with FAIR principles will be essential to achieving equitable access to high-quality, multi-dimensional datasets across the haemoglobinopathy research community.

4.4 Data Storage and Standardisation

Key Finding 4 (KF4): Heterogeneity in Storage Technologies and Lack of Standardisation

The survey revealed significant variability in data storage practices, with no single dominant system used across research institutions. A lack of standardisation in storage technologies and formats poses a considerable barrier to interoperability and multi-centre research efforts.

As shown in **Figure 7**, only 50% of respondents reported storing data locally in a dedicated research database. Findings indicate that 32% of respondents do not store data locally, while 18% were unsure of their data storage practices, suggesting inconsistencies in data management approaches. Among those who store data, Excel and REDCap were the most used technologies, often supplemented with additional tools. However, 36% of respondents who self-hosted their data were uncertain whether they followed standardised formats, and another 36% reported exclusively using custom or proprietary formats, creating challenges for data exchange and interoperability between institutions.

Figure 7: Local data storage practices among survey respondents. Doughnut chart illustrating whether respondents store data locally for research purposes and the associated storage technologies used.

The limited adoption of internationally recognised frameworks, such as FHIR (Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources) and OMOP (Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership), further hinders harmonised data integration (**Figure 8**). Without structured data storage solutions and standardised formats, data-sharing efforts remain fragmented, making it challenging to conduct large-scale, cross-institutional research.

Figure 8: Use of data storage standards. Bar chart showing reported adherence to data storage standards. The left panel displays standards for data stored locally, with custom formats being the most common. Widely recognised standards like FHIR and OMOP were rarely used.

Investing in standardised storage solutions, promoting adherence to FAIR data principles, and encouraging the broader adoption of interoperable data-sharing frameworks will be crucial in addressing these challenges.

4.5 Data Reuse and Collaboration

Key Finding 5 (KF5): Limited Integration and Interoperability of Haemoglobinopathy Data

The survey findings indicate significant variability in how haemoglobinopathy data is used for research. Due to non-standardised formats and limited interoperability, many datasets remain underutilised or difficult to integrate across institutions. Researchers were willing to collaborate, despite these challenges, mainly through models that preserved institutional data control.

As shown in **Figure 9**, survey responses indicate that 32% of respondents have never used their data for research. This suggests that while data is being collected, it is not actively analysed or utilised for scientific studies. In contrast, 63% of respondents have engaged in research using their data, with half having already

published results and the other half publishing their findings. Among those who have not yet conducted research, 82% expressed a willingness to collaborate, highlighting a strong potential for future data-sharing initiatives, whereas 18% were uninterested in participating in collaborative research efforts.

Have you already used your own data for research?

Figure 9: Respondents' reuse of their haemoglobinopathy data for research. Pie chart illustrating the proportion of respondents who have used their data for research. At the same time, 63% have used their data (either already published or ongoing), and 37% have not. A substantial number of non-users still expressed interest in future collaborative efforts, revealing untapped potential for data exploitation.

Table 3: Opportunities for collaboration. Breakdown of responses based on the answers from three different questions related to scientific collaboration. Among the centres that have not yet published their research, 4 responses (11% of the total) indicate a willingness to collaborate, as well as the availability of locally stored data.

	Do you store your data locally in a dedicated research database?	Willing to participate in multi-site collaboration	Number (and percentage) of responses
Already published research	yes	yes	7 (18%)
	no	yes	5 (16%)
	unknown	yes	3 (8%)
Ongoing unpublished research	yes	yes	7 (18%)

	no	yes	1 (3%)
	unknown	yes	2 (5%)
Data not exploited for research	yes	yes	4 (11%)
		no	1 (3%)
	no	yes	5 (13%)
		unknown	yes

In particular, 11% of the survey respondents indicated having locally-stored data and a willingness to collaborate, while an additional 13% were willing to collaborate but did not store their data locally (see Table 3). Compared to 3% of the survey respondents who are not willing to collaborate, this points to a large pool of centres who have not yet exploited their data for research but would be willing to, and in 11% of cases, have readily available retrospective data.

Preferences for collaborative research models varied based on data governance and privacy concerns. As shown in **Figure 10**, 84% of the survey respondents preferred a federated approach, where data remains locally stored but can be remotely accessed and analysed, ensuring greater control over data privacy and security. In contrast, only 53% were willing to contribute data to a centralised repository, with concerns primarily about privacy, governance, and institutional policies. This highlights the need for flexible, secure data-sharing frameworks that accommodate diverse institutional requirements.

Figure 10: Preferences for centralised versus federated collaborative research models. Funnel plots comparing participants’ willingness to engage in collaborative studies under different governance models. The left funnel (blue) shows responses to centralised data studies, and the right (red) shows responses to federated studies.

The preference for federated models highlights the importance of developing secure, privacy-preserving data-sharing infrastructures that support multi-centre collaboration while respecting data ownership and compliance regulations. Expanding federated frameworks, improving institutional data governance policies, and fostering standardised data-sharing agreements will be essential for maximising the impact of haemoglobinopathy datasets in research.

4.6 Data Privacy and Security

Key Finding 6 (KF6): Willingness to Collaborate but Limited Adoption of Data Privacy and Security Measures

The survey findings indicate inconsistencies in data anonymisation practices and institutional data retention policies, which may pose challenges for collaborative research and regulatory compliance. While many respondents expressed willingness to collaborate, the lack of standardised privacy measures highlights the need for additional support in implementing secure and compliant data-sharing frameworks.

Survey responses revealed significant gaps in data anonymisation practices. Only 29% of respondents had anonymised their data, indicating that most datasets remain identifiable. Additionally, 37% reported lacking the necessary resources for anonymisation, highlighting the need for institutional or infrastructural support to implement effective privacy-preserving measures. Those who have pseudonymised their data all relied on internal coding systems, with no respondents using external third-party anonymisation tools, suggesting a lack of standardised anonymisation frameworks across institutions.

Data retention policies were also inconsistently applied, with many institutions lacking formal strategies for long-term data management. The absence of clear retention policies raises concerns about data security, ethical compliance, and alignment with legal frameworks for data protection.

The findings highlight the need for standardised anonymisation protocols, improved institutional guidance on data retention, and the adoption of secure, privacy-preserving technologies. Strengthening data governance frameworks will ensure ethical and legally compliant data-sharing practices in haemoglobinopathy research.

4.7 General Comments

The final section included open-ended responses, providing additional feedback on challenges related to data sharing. These insights will guide future efforts to improve FAIR compliance and facilitate multi-centre collaboration.

A primary challenge for respondents in establishing collaboration and sharing data is obtaining approval from their institution or ethics committee. Once they secure institutional and ethical approval, the next step is obtaining patient consent. Another obstacle is that approvals for data sharing are often granted only under specific conditions, such as restricting research to Hemoglobinopathies. Additionally, one respondent noted that some data exist only in medical reports and are not available in an electronic format.

5. Challenges in Data Sharing: Promoting Standardised and FAIR Data Sharing in Haemoglobinopathies Research

Data sharing is fundamental for advancing scientific research and improving patient outcomes across various diseases, including haemoglobinopathies. However, implementing standardised and FAIR principles encounters substantial challenges in many diseases, such as fragmented data sources, variability in standards, ethical complexities, and resource constraints, as evidenced by studies in mental health, agriculture, and rare diseases (Hughes et al. 2023; Groot et al. 2024; Ugochukwu 2024; Sadeh et al. 2023). Addressing these challenges necessitates a comprehensive, cross-disciplinary approach to creating data ecosystems that facilitate effective collaboration and knowledge sharing.

5.1. Fragmentation of Data Sources

The landscape of haemoglobinopathy data is fragmented across various public repositories, unpublished diagnostic records, and diverse formats. This fragmentation leads to variability in data quality and accessibility, hindering the integration of datasets across National, European, and International research efforts (Hughes et al. 2023; Groot et al. 2024; Ugochukwu 2024; Sadeh et al. 2023).

Key Findings in Context

- ◆ Our results confirm this issue, as 35% of respondents reported using only custom or proprietary formats (KF4), demonstrating the extent of non-standard data practices.
- ◆ Moreover, limited interoperability (KF5) prevents effective data reuse. Only 53% of respondents are willing to contribute to centralised repositories, mainly due to data governance and standardisation concerns.

The lack of harmonised data collection and annotation practices further complicates data sharing and reuse, making it challenging for researchers to perform robust comparative studies. The absence of a centralised platform for unpublished diagnostic data also restricts opportunities for large-scale genotype-phenotype studies and collaborative analyses (Robinson 2017).

5.2. Efforts to address data fragmentation for Haemoglobinopathies

Several initiatives and collaborative efforts have been undertaken to tackle data fragmentation and enhance the integration of haemoglobinopathy-related datasets. For instance, projects like the RADeep platform and INHERENT have developed standardised data collection frameworks aligned with recognised ontologies such as the Human Phenotype Ontology (HPO), the Orphanet Rare Disease Ontology (ORDO) and the Sickle Cell Disease Ontology (SCDO). These models aim to harmonise data collection and annotation, enabling interoperability across study fields (Sadeh et al. 2023; Robinson 2017).

Key Findings in Context

- ◆ Our survey findings confirm regional disparities in data availability (KF3), with non-ITC countries reporting broader access to additional data types compared to ITC countries. This discrepancy reinforces the need for harmonised data collection to bridge data fragmentation.
- ◆ Similarly, KF5 highlights that 37% of respondents have never used their data for research, suggesting that fragmentation contributes to the underutilisation of datasets.

Centralised databases further address fragmentation. GenoMed4All, a federated platform, leverages artificial intelligence to enable personalised medicine in haematology, demonstrating how such systems can integrate fragmented datasets (Ugochukwu 2024). The ITHANET Portal also plays a critical role in reducing fragmentation by serving as a centralised, multi-functional resource for haemoglobinopathy-related data. It integrates a suite of interconnected tools—IthaGenes (a gene and variant repository), IthaMaps (a global epidemiology database), IthaPhen (a genotype-phenotype database), IthaChrom (HPLC data repository), and IthaCNV (a tool for studying structural variants). By bringing together genetic, clinical, epidemiological, and diagnostic information in a single, accessible platform, ITHANET enables researchers to explore complex datasets in a unified and interoperable environment, thereby directly tackling the issue of data fragmentation (Kountouris et al. 2014; Minaidou et al. 2022; Xenophontos et al. 2023).

Efforts to align datasets with FAIR principles also play a critical role. Platforms like REDCap support metadata standards, persistent identifiers, and enhanced discoverability (Groot et al. 2024; Hughes et al. 2023). The HemaFAIR project represents an excellent example of this approach, focusing on FAIRifying biomedical and clinical data in rare haematological diseases through standardised frameworks and harmonisation tools to support collaborative research.

Collaborative networks such as ERN-EuroBloodNet, INHERENT, and HELIOS further emphasise harmonised clinical and molecular data collection practices, promoting shared access to datasets across institutions (Groot et al. 2024; Ugochukwu 2024). Emerging tools, like electronic Case Report Forms (eCRFs) integrated

with REDCap (Harris et al. 2009; 2019), facilitate the storage and sharing of harmonised datasets, addressing accessibility and standardisation gaps (Sadeh et al. 2023; Robinson 2017).

Together, these efforts have significantly advanced the standardisation and accessibility of haemoglobinopathy data, laying the groundwork for improved collaboration and research outcomes. However, sustained efforts and additional resources are necessary to ensure these solutions are scalable, accessible, and widely adopted across diverse settings.

Key Findings in Context

- ◆ Our survey findings reinforce this challenge, showing significant heterogeneity in storage technologies (KF4). 35% of respondents do not store data locally, and 40% were unsure whether they follow standardised formats, illustrating a lack of structured data management.
- ◆ Additionally, KF6 highlights inconsistencies in anonymisation and retention policies, suggesting that data governance frameworks remain fragmented across institutions, further complicating standardisation efforts.

5.3. Remaining Barriers to Data Sharing

Variability in Data Standards

Data standards across institutions and countries vary significantly, creating challenges for interoperability and integration. For example, datasets often lack alignment with widely recognised ontologies such as the HPO or the SCDO, resulting in incompatible definitions, formats and inconsistent metadata annotations (Angastiniotis et al. 2023). These inconsistencies prevent seamless data sharing between stakeholders and hinder large-scale comparative studies. Furthermore, while some projects have developed domain-specific ontologies, their adoption remains inconsistent, and legacy datasets frequently rely on outdated or private schemas, exacerbating the problem.

Efforts to address these challenges have included developing universal data standards and promoting their

adoption through training and capacity-building initiatives. However, implementing such standards across diverse research environments is still limited, leaving a significant gap in global data interoperability.

Limited Compliance with FAIR Principles

Despite increasing awareness of the importance of FAIR principles, compliance remains low in haemoglobinopathy-related research. Factors such as inadequate metadata, restrictive access policies, and outdated storage technologies contribute to the reduced findability and accessibility of datasets (Kountouris et al., 2021). Additionally, proprietary formats often limit interoperability, making it challenging for researchers to reuse data efficiently.

Some initiatives, such as HemaFAIR and ITHANET, have developed frameworks to encourage the FAIRification of datasets. These include persistent identifiers, improved metadata standards, and repositories with FAIR-compliant interfaces. However, many researchers lack the technical expertise or resources to fully implement these measures, highlighting the need for user-friendly tools and targeted training.

Key Findings in Context

- ◆ Our survey found significant inconsistencies in anonymisation and data retention policies (KF6), with 42% of respondents lacking the resources to anonymise their data.
- ◆ 27% of respondents had already anonymised their data. Still, all relied on internal coding systems, with no respondents using external third-party anonymisation tools, indicating a lack of standardised anonymisation protocols.

Ethical and Regulatory Barriers

Ethical considerations and regulatory frameworks present significant challenges to data sharing, particularly in cross-border collaborations. Concerns regarding patient privacy, diverse legal requirements, and varying standards for informed consent further complicate the sharing of sensitive data. For instance, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in the European Union stipulates robust mechanisms to safeguard patient anonymity. However, differences in interpretation across member states add complexity to the compliance (Cheah et al. 2018).

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Additionally, the lack of harmonised guidelines for data anonymisation often leads to inconsistent practices, potentially exposing patients to privacy risks or limiting the usability of shared data. While collaborative networks like ERN-EuroBloodNet, INHERENT and HELIOS have sought to address these issues by developing standardised consent frameworks, further work is needed to ensure widespread adoption and alignment.

Resource and Expertise Constraints

Resource limitations, particularly in settings with constrained financial, technical, or infrastructural capacity, pose significant challenges to adopting advanced data-sharing technologies and FAIR principles. These low-resource settings may include underfunded institutions within higher-income countries and entire regions in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), where systemic challenges often limit access to modern data management tools and training (Twum et al. 2023).

Such disparities exacerbate inequities in data sharing and reduce the global availability of high-quality datasets. Addressing these gaps requires targeted capacity-building programs, sustainable funding mechanisms, and collaborative initiatives to ensure that resource-constrained environments can participate meaningfully in data-sharing ecosystems.

Key Findings in Context

- ◆ KF3 highlights regional disparities in dataset availability, where ITC countries reported lower access to specialised datasets.
- ◆ KF4 indicates a lack of standardised storage solutions, making data governance even more complex for underfunded institutions.

Technological Limitations

Outdated databases, insufficient computational infrastructure, and a lack of interoperability tools impede the implementation of effective data-sharing practices. Many existing systems were not designed to manage contemporary biomedical datasets' volume, variety, and complexity, resulting in inefficiencies and data loss during integration efforts (Hughes et al. 2023).

To overcome these technological barriers, developing user-friendly tools and infrastructures for data

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integration and analysis has become a priority. Emerging projects such as RADeep, GenoMed4All, and INHERENT demonstrate how innovative approaches can begin to address these gaps.

RADeep is a pan-European patient registry for rare anaemias, offering a structured, interoperable platform that supports standardised data capture and aggregation across institutions. GenoMed4All harnesses AI technologies to perform advanced analyses on harmonised datasets, facilitating predictive modelling and personalised care pathways. Meanwhile, INHERENT collects detailed genetic and clinical data on haemoglobinopathy patients to improve diagnosis, data harmonisation, and treatment planning through standardised data formats and FAIR-compliant practices.

These projects highlight the potential of modern technologies to improve data infrastructure, but their broader adoption and scalability remain essential to ensure lasting impact across the haemoglobinopathy research landscape.

Key Findings in Context

- ◆ KF5 and KF6 demonstrate that most respondents are open to federated data-sharing models, provided privacy, standardisation, and governance frameworks are strengthened.

6. Moving Forward: Strengthening Collaboration and Data Interoperability

This report highlights significant challenges and promising opportunities for advancing haemoglobinopathy research through standardised data-sharing models, FAIR principles, and collaborative networks. Addressing data fragmentation, technological heterogeneity, and privacy concerns requires a structured approach that leverages existing synergies while building new frameworks for data interoperability.

Strengthening Synergies with Existing Initiatives

Several ongoing projects, including RADeep, ITHANET, GenoMed4All, and HemaFAIR, have made important strides in data integration, accessibility, and standardisation by developing interoperable registries, promoting FAIR principles, and applying advanced tools such as AI for data analysis. Platforms like RADeep and ITHANET offer structured, standardised datasets and serve as valuable resources for improving interoperability, making them well-aligned with HELIOS objectives. Similarly, ERN-EuroBloodNet and

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INHERENT are key initiatives in developing registries and datasets that conform to FAIR principles, providing a strong foundation for broader collaboration and harmonised data-sharing practices in line with international standards.

Next Steps: Building a FAIR and Interoperable Data Ecosystem

To translate survey insights into actionable improvements, key steps will focus on developing a Data Interoperability Framework that ensures structured, standardised, and shareable datasets across research institutions.

Efforts will also include testing centralised and federated data-sharing models to accommodate different institutional needs and privacy constraints while maintaining compliance with ethical and regulatory standards.

Training workshops on FAIR principles, standardised metadata usage, and data-sharing compliance will also be implemented to build capacity across research teams and foster a more collaborative and interoperable data ecosystem.

Key Recommendations for Advancing Data Sharing

A strategic approach is essential to overcome the barriers identified in this report. Efforts should focus on aligning with FAIR principles through targeted training, guidelines, and practical resources to facilitate adoption. Efforts should also include improving funding mechanisms for anonymisation tools and ensuring institutions can comply with data privacy regulations while maintaining dataset usability. Additionally, establishing centralised registries for unpublished diagnostic data will enable more comprehensive genotype-phenotype studies and enhance multi-centre research collaborations, strengthening the haemoglobinopathy research ecosystem.

By addressing these areas, the haemoglobinopathy research community can move towards a more integrated, standardised, and FAIR-compliant data ecosystem, ultimately enhancing collaborative research, patient outcomes, and scientific discovery.

7. Conclusion

This report comprehensively analyses the current landscape of haemoglobinopathy data availability, storage, standardisation, and sharing practices. Through survey findings, we identified key challenges related to data fragmentation, lack of interoperability, inconsistent adoption of FAIR principles, and privacy concerns. Despite these barriers, stakeholders are strongly willing to collaborate, mainly through federated data-sharing models, allowing controlled access while ensuring data privacy and security.

Findings indicate significant regional disparities in data availability, with non-ITC countries having greater access to specialised datasets such as imaging and coded diagnosis records. In contrast, ITC countries often lack the necessary data standardisation and infrastructure for interoperability. Additionally, the reliance on heterogeneous storage solutions and proprietary formats further limits cross-institutional data exchange and reuse.

To address these issues, targeted efforts must strengthen international collaborations, invest in standardisation frameworks, and promote sustainable data governance strategies. Initiatives such as RADeep, ITHANET, GenoMed4All, HemaFAIR, and ERN-EuroBloodNet are valuable resources for advancing interoperability and ensuring compliance with FAIR principles.

Moving forward, priority should be given to:

- **Developing a Data Interoperability Framework** to align research datasets with standardised, shareable formats.
- **Expanding federated data-sharing models** to balance privacy with accessibility.
- **Implementing structured training programs** to enhance capacity in FAIR-compliant data management.
- **Improving funding mechanisms** for anonymisation tools and data security infrastructure.
- **Establishing central registries for unpublished diagnostic data** to maximise research potential and cross-border collaboration.

By taking these steps, the haemoglobinopathy research community can overcome current data-sharing limitations, foster more integrated multi-centre studies, and accelerate advancements in diagnosis and

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treatment. Ensuring the broad adoption of FAIR principles and sustainable data governance will be crucial in building a harmonised and accessible research ecosystem, ultimately benefiting both scientific progress and patient care.

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9. Annexe

Survey Questionnaire

<https://redcap.heliosaction.eu/surveys/?s=RCYF3YPKHHFA8XM3>

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Supplementary Table

Table S1: Collaborative initiatives in Haemoglobinopathy research.

Project	Description	Geographical Coverage	Website/Publication Reference
ARISE	Aims to improve research capacity and innovation in the field of sickle cell disease and thalassemia, particularly in underrepresented regions.	Africa	https://www.ariseinitiative.org
ENROL	The central registry of the ERN-EuroBloodNet on Rare Haematological Diseases (RHD) acts as an umbrella for both new and existing European patients' registries.	Europe	https://enrolnetwork.eu/
ERN-EuroBlood Net	The European Reference Network (ERN) for rare haematological diseases, including haemoglobinopathies, facilitates collaboration and knowledge exchange among specialists.	Europe	https://www.eurobloodnet.eu
HemaFAIR	Established by international collaborations that are experts in their field, aiming to raise the scientific profile and competitiveness of CING in the fields of biomedical informatics and RHDs, with a focus on the use of FAIR data and standards in research and education.	Cyprus	https://hemafairproject.eu/hemafair/

GenoMed4ALL	An open-source data hub for haematological diseases by adopting groundbreaking and trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (AI) algorithms.	Europe	https://genomed4all.eu/
INHERENT	A collaborative initiative focused on standardising and harmonising genetic and clinical data for haemoglobinopathy patients to improve diagnosis and treatment.	Worldwide	https://inherent-h2020.eu
RADeep	An initiative conceived at the core of ERN-EuroBloodNet to act as an umbrella for new and existing European patients with rare anaemia disorders (RAD).	Europe	https://www.radeepnetwork.eu/
Sickle In Africa	Focuses on advancing research and healthcare infrastructure for sickle cell disease and thalassemia in African nations.	Africa	https://www.sickleinafrica.org
THALAMOSS	A research initiative focused on integrating genetic and genomic information to better understand disease severity and treatment response in beta-thalassaemia and sickle cell disease, to develop personalised therapies that enhance foetal haemoglobin production and improve patient outcomes.	Europe, USA	http://www.thalamoss.eu/
Other	Represents respondents involved in international projects that were not explicitly listed but still contribute to haemoglobinopathy research.	Not Applicable	Not Applicable

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